

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

AUDIT AS THE MAIN CONDITION FOR INCREASE OF THE TRANSPARENCY OF BUDGET PROCESS AND ESTABLISHMENT OF EFFECTIVE ACCOUNTABILITY MECHANISM

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Abstract

The effective organization of legal relations being the basis of public finances is one of the key and priority issues facing every country. The aspiration to control in terms of ensuring full coverage may make the issues of problem specification a subject of analysis and professional deliberations including the reliability of the alternatives to achieving goals and subprograms involving non-financial products. The possibilities of projecting of the measures that will allow to correctly rearrange the regulation of the conditions necessary for the operation of the demand-responsibility chain from the point of view of a purposeful strategy review become clear by the sum of the additional issues raised in the current period and the issues raised within the framework of the accumulated experience. In the quantitative-qualitative flow-parallel processes, the consolidation of conclusions with the qualitative advantage of audit and the use in time by necessity is definite. In the current reality, the organization of the regular budget process in line with a new model supposes the division of the work of forming an institution of responsibility and ensuring transparency, with the aim of eliminating the various gaps between separate stages in anticipation of their unification in the upcoming periods.

Keywords: public participation, Audit Chamber, transparency, strategic reforms, effectiveness.

The public financial relations include the widest range of public participation, so the budget system currently formed in RA, as the subject base of public finances, carries the mission of defining priorities, clarifying the various issues existing at the level of state administration and local self-government bodies, under the issue of the provision of close connection with strategic priorities, as a result of combining existing and possible financial resources. The risks of overcoming external challenges and obstacles to the stabilization of the internal environment in the context of situational budget regulation, the processing and implementation of budget policy propose necessary arrangements to identify opportunities for professional preparedness and abilities improvement, with the aim of localizing more accurate methodological provision of probabilistic calculations of forecasts in the real regime.

The purpose of the reforms of the State Finance Management System is to increase the efficiency of state expenses management, in particular, to ensure financial and budgetary discipline and thereby contribute to the establishment of macroeconomic stability. The current chronological changes in the State Finance Management System will certainly form rearrangements from the point of view of the review of the goal-result strategy, in particular, the following will be considered as important:

- The raise of main institutional and legal issues related to reforms
- The full provision of the participation process
- The outline of ways of solution of current and far-reaching issues in the matter of goal-result provision
- The assessment and monitoring of targets and indicators foreseen by the strategy[1].

The reflection of the mentioned rearrangements in the State Finance Management System is highly desirable until the continuity of the necessary steps confirms the start of their queue as a new sub-layer of the reforms implemented in RA. Since 2012, the implementation of legislative, in particular, accountability reforms has been aimed at improving internal and external control processes. However, in retrospect, the logic of the replacement of studies and analyzes with control was fixed in article 1 of the RA Law "On the Control Chamber of the RA National Assembly" since in 1999[2]. But, in fact, the replacement of traditional budgeting with a different of modern budgeting caused difficulties even in the long-term period in terms of improving control mechanisms. Taking into account that from the beginning the problems of the Control Chamber were summed up with the component of methodical and professional assistance, even today this problem is relevant at the audit level[3].

The importance of the independent audit in terms of improving the budgeting process puts a special emphasis on the performance control from the 4 types of control, considering the decision of the effectiveness of achieving the set goal[4]. At present, it is a priority to introduce the evaluation mechanisms from the goals of the budget programs to the result indicators, as well as the harmonization of individual elements in the strategic planning system[5]. Internal control processes are greatly promoted from an organizational point of view within the framework of the expansion of external control functions, constantly providing opportunities for the expansion of methodological support. At the end of the cycle of the budget process, the main actor of control-responsibility issues is the RA Audit Chamber, and in order to improve the effectiveness of external control, a sub-Committee on Accounting and Audit issues was formed in the RA National Assembly's Financial

Credit and Budget Committee, which should become a platform for cooperation with the Audit Chamber[6]. Currently, the frequency of studies and analyzes in the state audit procedures will also contribute to the above, conditioned by the positive experience of the current conclusions being rooted in the RA[7]. It should be also noted that in the continuation of the work on the introduction of the structures foreseen by the RA Law on "Accounting and Auditing Activity Regulation and Public Control" it is planned to introduce the mechanisms of public control of audit quality, which will allow to increase the quality of provided audit services and public trust[8].

In our country, the legislative body is the main actor in forming the mechanism for reversing the inefficiency of the known version of circulation of public order in legal, political, socio-economic and other platforms, but from the point of view of realization, the main role of the Audit Chamber becomes primary in today's reality, because on the side of the experimental application being conditioned by the time factor, it is necessary to put forward a number of conditions until the starting grounds of the above scenario are visible.

It is clear that the separate outline of the necessary condition is not enough for the full clarification of the issue of transparency and responsibility of the budget process, but over the years it becomes the cornerstone of the chain continuous processes in the sense that it is the culmination of the optimization of the improvement of the further documentation of the experimental application. As we know, the field of desires is formed in the private and public sector, the latter limits it within the range of resource availability of the public order. In this case, the initiating legislative power "enforces" the fulfillment of the public demand at the expense of the replenishing effective practices of the executive power.

The Audit Chamber, even as a result of the current control work, is unable to have a significant impact on the improvement of the ongoing works, that is why the schedule of the clarification of problems, the check-up and verification of calculations on the line of the Audit Chamber is moved to the following periods, and the responsibility for the resulting improvements is assumed from the executive to the legislative in a dialogue domain. According to this logic, ensuring the comprehensiveness of the budget process under the conditions of full public participation will ultimately move the beneficiary oriented policy to a qualitatively higher level, when the reinunerativeness will become secondary in comparison with the ideology of public benefit.

Since the strategic reforms in the budget sector have just have recently started in the local self-government system, we consider it as important to note that in the communal processes the localization of the achievements at the state management level will require a lot of time in terms of institutional reforms, but it is obvious that the practicality of realizing results can become confirmed even under the conditions of the absence of information documents circulation. The current processes in the communities, and the fundamental and complete changes of the information base in the state management system will not only become complemen-

tary processes, but will confirm the urgency and indisputability of the common-good work through the transfer regime of mutual assistance.

The investment of the program budgeting system has caused many difficulties in different countries, but having reached the necessary replenishment of public finances management reforms at the level of responsibility, it becomes realistic not only to identify, prevent and reduce the existing obstacles with the value system structure, but also to minimize the existing risks caused by these obstacles by rooting the principle of transparency. Transparency is progressive as compared with the reordering of Public Finance Management priorities from a purely temporal due to the influence of time.

Speaking in detail on the above, it should be mentioned that the visibility of the recovery of the mentioned circle with the comprehensive participation of the relevant bodies supposes at least the cessation of "double-edged striker" policy, which will make it possible not only to regulate the boundaries of the powers within the framework of the authorities, but also to pave the way to mitigate the negative perception of responsibility by the establishment of an effective consulting regime. As the second most important step, it will form an ability to convert the impossibility of visibility of problems by taking the necessary measures for their disclosure, prevention, specification of optimal solutions, and constantly rise in the hierarchy of efficiency.

From a strategic point of view, the control function is finally established at the level of monitoring, but within the framework of tactical planning, parallel initiatives to maintain the legality, effectiveness and other principles of the problems known to us will continue, and in the case of newly emerging and seemingly unsolvable problems, it will be necessary to determine the following sequence of steps in order to pass from the first level of overcoming of effectiveness to the next one:

- The identification of a problem that contains or does not contain a risk,
- The consideration of the proposed solutions for the solution of a problem at the highest possible level, setting the goal of the Program budgeting reforms as the first level,
- Outcome-based monitoring of the time-scale prevalence of financial and non-financial evaluation at the level of arrangement, and so on.

As we see, such an approach can sometimes form the exact opposite ideas regarding such compliances, whose discovery has always been justified in terms of the expectations of non-laborious processes. We think that at certain turning points in the following periods, establishing reliability and compliance can be formed as a result of the simultaneous implementation of other principles of Program budgeting.

References:

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4. The RA Law "On the Control Chamber", December 25, 2006, article 4

5. The strategy of the State Finance Management System Reforms 2019-2023, p 15

6. The strategy of the State Finance Management System Reforms 2019-2023, p 55

7. The RA Law "On the Audit Chamber", January 16, 2018, article 5, point 4.1, sub-point "c"

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